

A Quark mass/charge formula

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Current estimates [1] of Quark masses vary from the lightest Up (**u**) ~ 2.3 to the heaviest Top (**t**) 173,210, measured in units of MeV/c^2 . The table below shows the masses and corresponding fractional charges.

Quark		Mass	Charge
Name	Symbol	MeV/c^2	e
Up	u	2.3	+2/3
Down	d	4.8	-1/3
Charm	c	1275	+2/3
Strange	s	95	-1/3
Top	t	173210	+2/3
Bottom	b	4180	-1/3

Given the wide disparity in masses, let's plot them on a log scale, top tier below; the lower tier has the corresponding fractional charges. The abscissa is (**u, d, c, s, t, b**), as in the table order.

Intrigued by the periodic appearance of ordered masses on a log-scale, let's apply $\cos(\log(.))$; result below.

From here, numerical experiments revealed a connection between masses and fractional charges, requiring, however, some significant alterations in mass. Let

m_q = altered Quark mass vector (MeV/c^2) = $[\mathbf{u} \ \mathbf{d} \ \mathbf{c} \ \mathbf{s} \ \mathbf{t} \ \mathbf{b}] = [2.4 \ 5.1 \ 1,260 \ 105 \ 122,000 \ 2,730]$
 ch = Quark fractional charges vector = $[2/3 \ -1/3 \ 2/3 \ -1/3 \ 2/3 \ -1/3]$

A mass/charge model is

$$\mathbf{A) \ } \cos(\log(m_q)) = (1 + 4ch)/5.6$$

to an error of less than **.005**.

Some of the altered masses - to fit model **A**) - differ greatly from the currently accepted values listed in the table above on page 1, most obviously the Top (**t**) Quark.

Now, to express Quark mass directly as a function of fractional charge, let

$$\mathbf{ach} = (1 + 4ch)/5.6$$

an altered fractional charge vector (as it were) for the set $[\mathbf{u} \ \mathbf{d} \ \mathbf{c} \ \mathbf{s} \ \mathbf{t} \ \mathbf{b}]$:

$$\mathbf{ach} = \text{altered Quark fractional charges vector} = 5[11/84 \ -1/84 \ 11/84 \ -1/84 \ 11/84 \ -1/84]$$

Then

$$\mathbf{B) \ } m_q = \exp(\text{acos}(\text{ach}) + K\pi)$$

for some constant (mostly integer) **K** dependent on each Quark; mass estimates are shown below, fairly consistent with values on top of this page.

$$\mathbf{K(u)} = 0 \Rightarrow \text{mass(u)} = 2.4$$

$$\mathbf{K(d)} = 0 \Rightarrow \text{mass(d)} = 5.1$$

$$\mathbf{K(c)} = 2 \Rightarrow \text{mass(c)} = 1,261$$

$$\mathbf{K(s)} = 1 \Rightarrow \text{mass(s)} = 118$$

$$\mathbf{K(t)} = 3.4552 \Rightarrow \text{mass(t)} = 121,998$$

$$\mathbf{K(b)} = 2 \Rightarrow \text{mass(b)} = 2,734$$

It is unsatisfying that the Top Quark (**t**) mass does not result from an integer constant in model **B**); some such would yield

$$\mathbf{K(t)} = 3 \Rightarrow \text{mass(t)} = 29,194$$

$$\mathbf{K(t)} = 4 \Rightarrow \text{mass(t)} = 675,561$$

Even better, the choices

$$\mathbf{K(t)} = 3.5668 \Rightarrow \text{mass(t)} = 173,228$$

$$\mathbf{K(b)} = 2.135 \Rightarrow \text{mass(b)} = 4,178$$

lead to values consistent with accepted masses for both (**t**) and (**b**).

Reference

[1] Wikipedia article on Quarks.